

AGE DEPENDENT CHARACTERISTICS OF 1-2 AGE LARVAE OF TURNIP MOTH (AGROTIS SEGETUM DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775)

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Annotation. Age-related characteristics of 1-year-old larvae of turnip moth were studied. The changes that occur in the body parts of the worm after hatching and until the end of the 1st year or the time of hatching are described.

A number of scientists have given descriptions of the stages of development and different ages of the worms of the autumn nightshade, and the main attention has been given to the classification of the worms according to such characters as body color, head and body size. However, the detailed description of the location of the spots on the back of the autumn moth caterpillar, taking into account the fact that it is typical not only for the autumn caterpillar, but also for the larvae of some other species of butterflies, it is recognized that it is difficult to determine the distribution ratio of most caterpillars in nature according to the given characters, and reported the importance of head capsule measurements to determine the age of autumn caterpillars [1,3].

Detailed descriptions of the larval stage of the autumn moth are known from some studies, and these studies focus not only on the features specific to the larvae of the autumn moth, but also on the differentiation of the characters of the autumn and exclamation moths [2].

In some scientific sources, the ecology of larvae of all ages of the autumn caterpillar is covered in detail, but little attention is paid to the size of worms depending on age [4].

In the conditions of the Fergana region, researches related to the distribution and pest characteristics of the autumn caterpillar were conducted, and no information was recorded on the age-related characteristics of the worms [5,6].

Differences in the larval stage of the autumn nightshade by young people are not sufficiently substantiated by numbers. The color and size of the body in such cases show a wide variety, so we focused on the signs that do not change during life. As such a sign, importance was attached to qualitative and quantitative changes occurring in the body length of the worm at the time of

hatching and the width of the head capsule, which does not always change in size.

The 1st instar of worms begins with the process of breaking the egg shell. By gnawing on the eggshell, it makes a hole below the top of the egg (rarely above the top of the egg) and slowly expands it.

It feeds by swallowing gnawed parts. After hatching, the worms feed on the soft part of the leaves in the case of a plant, or they can gnaw it and make small holes. If the worm has hatched in a non-plant (soil) or dry plant, it can move to other places or climb plants. But as a result of underdeveloped abdominal legs and growths on them, worms cannot stand firmly on plants or other places.

The color of the head of the worm that hatched from the egg is black and has a shiny appearance. The head is divided into three parts, two of which are convex on the sides, and the third reaches from the base to the upper lip, in the form of a triangle, and the apex reaches the border of the head with the first thoracic segment. . The front part of the head has a pair of tentacles ending in short spines. The upper jaw of the worm is dark-brown in color.

Head capsule width $0,33+0,001\text{mm}$. The color of the worm when it hatches is yellowish-gray, after feeding, it turns gray-green due to the visibility of the intestine through the chitin coating. On the first thoracic segment of the body, a back neck shield appears, almost the same color as the head. The last abdominal segment has a second shield of the same color. The whole body of the worm is made up of 11 clearly distinguishable segments, and the back is covered with black dots.

From each of the points comes a long brown blade, ending in a knob-like thickening. The color of the sword, thickened like a club, is liquid, and the tip of the sword looks like a small drop of water. Similar spines are present on the head of the worm and on both shields. The worm's body is naked from below. Beneath each of the three segments is a pair of true legs, each ending in a sharp, light-brown claw.

The first, second and third abdominal segments do not have legs. On the fourth segment is the inconspicuous base of a pair of abdominal legs, and on the fifth and sixth segments there is a pair of well-defined false legs. The seventh and eighth segments are similarly devoid of legs, and the last, ninth segment has a third distinct set of abdominal legs. On both sides of the worm's body there are nine pairs of respiratory holes in the form of round holes with a dark brown circular border, these holes are surrounded by black plate-like dots. Air vents

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are located on the first thoracic and 1-8 abdominal segments, the first and last pairs are much larger than the others.

When the ratio of the length of the body of the 1st year worm to the width of the head capsule ("A" index) is determined using the Kosobutsky formula ($A=P/Q$ where P is the length of the worm body and Q is the width of the head capsule), the A-index is 9.37 ± 0.17 . It was found to be equal to 0.17.

The width of the head capsule of the second instar worm is 0.62 ± 0.0012 mm. The head of the worm turns white after molting at the end of the first instar. Later, the color of the head becomes darker. It is lighter in color compared to the color of the head capsule in the first-year belts. At the head of the worm, two triangles with the ends pointing in different directions are intended. One of these is larger in size, and its base is directed towards the upper lip, and the base of the other is directed towards the chest segment. In fact, the second triangle is formed as a result of a fold on the side of the head, and this fold cuts out a small triangular area that fits into the central recess of the head.

This triangular area may not be present when the worm's body is extremely elongated before hatching. Later, the body of the worm becomes striped, and the color of the body becomes brownish-gray. The striped appearance is caused by an odd number of oozing stripes down the middle of the body, with two darker, brownish stripes alternating with two oozing stripes on either side. The tufted thickenings of the hair tend to stretch along the length, so the tufted look is less exaggerated. The pair of false legs in the fourth abdominal segment is better expressed than in the first age; in addition, in the third abdominal segment there is an incomplete base of the last eighth pair of legs. The heel of the false legs of the second instar worm is more clearly defined, and the third pair of false legs now has 5-6 claws, and the fourth pair has 7-8 claws. When the worm feeds on the leaves of various plants, it completely pierces them, and in some cases it can even gnaw at the edges.

The ratio of the length of the body of the worm of the second age to the width of the head capsule ("A" index) was found to be equal to 8.56 ± 0.17 .

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